

Calcd. for $C_{17}H_{12}O_6N_6$; N, 21.21%. Its ir spectrum showed bands at 3280 (NH), 1690 (C=O), 1620 (C=N), 1610 and 1590 (phenyl), 1375 and 1336 (NO_2) cm^{-1} .

Reaction of ninhydrin with thiourea. Formation of 1,3-diketohydrindylidene-2-thiocarbamide (VII): The reaction mixture was stirred for 70 hr. A white precipitate obtained as (VII) was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 228-229°, yield 64.5% (Found: N, 12.40; S, 15.02. Calcd. for $C_{10}H_6O_2N_2S$; N, 12.84; S, 14.67%). The 2,4-DNP derivative crystallised from ethanol, m.p. 247-249° (Found: N, 20.62; S, 7.76. Calcd. for $C_{16}H_{10}O_5N_6S$; N, 21.10; S, 8.04%).

References

1. S. BUHMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1438.
2. R. MOUBASHER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1038.
3. M. FRIEDMAN, *Canad. J. Chem.*, 1967, 45, 2271.
4. R. SHAFIRO and N. CHATTERJEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1970, 35, 447.
5. D. A. MACFADYAN, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1950, 186, 1.
6. N. POLONOVSKI, P. COUNARD and G. GOITZ, *Bull. Soc. Chem.*, 1939, 6, 1557.
7. D. D. VANSLYKE and P. B. HAMILTON, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1943, 150, 471.
8. M. G. AHMED, A. HYE and M. AHMED, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 594.
9. M. G. AHMED and A. RAHIM, *Bangladesh J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1975, 10, 291.
10. M. G. AHMED, S. A. AHMED, U. Q. R. ROMMAN and M. K. ALAM, *J. Bangladesh Acad. Sci.*, 1981, 5, 13.

Potential Antithyroid Agents. Part-II : Synthetic and Pharmacological Studies on Some N-Aryl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocar- bamides and N-aryl-N'-benzenesulphonyl- thiocarbamides

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THE antithyroid agents lower the metabolic rate by interfering with the synthesis, release or peripheral action of the thyroid hormone. Highly active antithyroid substances contain thiourea moieties, -NHCSNH-, capable of being easily oxidized and it has been suggested that the interference with thyroxine synthesis is by direct reaction between I_2 and SH (formed by enolization) to form a disulphide¹⁻⁴.

The present communication deals with the synthesis and pharmacological studies of some

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N-aryl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamides and N-aryl-N'-benzenesulphonylthiocarbamides. The active antithyroid drug is carbimazole consisting of an imidazole nucleus. Therefore, it was of interest to prepare some benzimidazolyl thiocarbamides consisting of a benzimidazole nucleus alongwith an extra thioureylene group, by the action of arylisothiocyanates with 2-aminobenzimidazole. The interest in the synthesis and pharmacological studies of benzenesulphonylthiocarbamides as antithyroid drug is due to the fact that these compounds contain an extra sulphonamide grouping alongwith the thioureylene linkages. The synthesis has been effected by the condensation of benzenesulphonyl-isothiocyanate with appropriate aromatic amines.

Experimental

Melting points were determined with a Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra were obtained using KBr pellets and a Perkin-Elmer 720 Infracord spectrophotometer; bands reported were at least of medium intensity. Elemental analyses were in good agreement with the theoretical values.

Arylisothiocyanates: These have been prepared according to the method reported in the literature⁵.

Benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate: It has been synthesised by the method of McFarland and Houser⁶.

N-Phenyl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamide: A mixture of phenylisothiocyanate (2.7 g; 0.02 mole) and 2-aminobenzimidazole (2.66 g; 0.02 mole) in dry benzene (25 ml) was refluxed for 2 hr. After the reaction, the excess benzene was distilled off and the residue was washed with petroleum ether (40-60°) and finally with ether to remove any unreacted constituents. N-Phenyl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamide thus formed was recrystallised from ethanol. It could be desulphured with alkaline plumbite solution, yield 4.2 g, 80%; m.p. 110°. Anal. Found: C, 62.62; H, 4.38; N, 20.82; S, 11.90. Calcd. for $C_{14}H_{12}N_4S$; C, 62.68; H, 4.47; N, 20.89; S, 11.94%.

Other N-aryl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamides were prepared similarly by the condensation of 2-aminobenzimidazole with different arylisothiocyanates.

The various N-aryl-N'-2(benzimidazolyl) thiocarbamides were characterised by elemental analyses. Presence of characteristic bands of $N=C=S$ (1520 cm^{-1}) and substituted benzene ring (780 cm^{-1}) in the ir spectra of these compounds provided further confirmation of their molecular structure.

N-Phenyl-N'-benzenesulphonylthiocarbamide: A solution of aniline (1.86 g; 0.02 mole) in benzene (20 ml) was gradually added to a solution of benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate (3.98 g; 0.02 mole) in benzene (20 ml). After few min a white precipitate of N-phenyl-N'-benzenesulphonylthiocarbamide was formed, which was collected and washed with benzene, petroleum ether (40-60°) and finally with

NOTES

TABLE 1—SYNTHETIC AND PHARMACOLOGICAL SCREENING RESULTS OF N-ARYL-N'-2(BENZIMIDAZOLYL) THIOCARBAMIDES AND N-ARYL-N'-BENZENESULPHONYLTHIOCARBAMIDES AS ANTITHYROID DRUGS IN INTACT RATS

No.	Compound		Yield %	m.p. °C	Thyroid radioactivity (dpm ± standard error)		Inorganic ¹³¹ I	Approximate estimated activity in rats (thiouracil=1.0)
	R ¹	R			¹³¹ I:uptake	PB ¹³¹ I		
1.		H	80	110	3662 ± 12	2842 ± 15	738 ± 32	>1
2.	-do-	2-CH ₃	72	150	3546 ± 42	2985 ± 25	510 ± 14	>1
3.	-do-	3-CH ₃	70	78	3682 ± 40	2781 ± 15	886 ± 28	>1
4.	-do-	4-CH ₃	74	65	3487 ± 50	3083 ± 22	430 ± 14	>1
5.	-do-	2-OCH ₃	75	70	4234 ± 38	3679 ± 13	530 ± 16	>1
6.	-do-	4-OCH ₃	78	80	4386 ± 24	3812 ± 18	526 ± 11	<1
7.	-do-	2-Cl	74	60	3165 ± 22	2517 ± 12	619 ± 15	>1
8.	-do-	3-Cl	72	80	3286 ± 30	2452 ± 14	802 ± 24	>1
9.	-do-	4-Cl	75	155	3132 ± 24	2367 ± 24	714 ± 17	>1
10.	-do-	4-OC ₂ H ₅	78	130	3614 ± 15	2937 ± 26	655 ± 16	>1
11.	C ₆ H ₅ SO ₂	H	90	120	5522 ± 19	4897 ± 23	587 ± 12	<1
12.	-do-	2-CH ₃	85	130	5731 ± 15	5126 ± 10	578 ± 14	<1
13.	-do-	3-CH ₃	80	140	5653 ± 18	5120 ± 17	506 ± 19	<1
14.	-do-	4-CH ₃	82	124	5613 ± 12	4976 ± 20	612 ± 14	<1
15.	-do-	2-OCH ₃	78	122	4602 ± 25	4123 ± 12	465 ± 18	<1
16.	-do-	4-OCH ₃	76	132	4598 ± 16	3976 ± 14	592 ± 13	<1
17.	-do-	2-Cl	68	130	4427 ± 12	3792 ± 18	603 ± 11	>1
18.	-do-	3-Cl	70	136	4398 ± 20	3688 ± 16	678 ± 24	>1
19.	-do-	4-Cl	74	125	4265 ± 14	3661 ± 13	569 ± 21	>1
20.	-do-	4-OC ₂ H ₅	72	102	5836 ± 24	5189 ± 11	620 ± 15	<1
21.		Control (Blank)			8478 ± 50	7196 ± 42	1238 ± 28	
22.		Thiouracil			4463 ± 62	3822 ± 30	620 ± 18	1.0

* Concentrations of test compounds equimolar to thiouracil ; the analytical results for C, H, N and S in these compounds agreed with ±0.5% of the theoretical values.

ether to remove any unreacted constituents. The thiocarbamide thus obtained was recrystallized from ethanol, and could be desulphured with alkaline plumbite solution, yield 5.75 g, 90%; m.p. 120°. Anal. Found : C, 53.30 ; H, 4.02 ; N, 9.52 ; S, 21.88. Calcd. for C₁₃H₁₂N₂O₂S₂ ; C, 53.42 ; H, 4.10 ; N, 9.58 ; S, 21.91%.

Similarly, other N-aryl-N'-benzenesulphonylthiocarbamides were prepared by condensing benzenesulphonylisothiocyanate with different amines and they are listed in Table 1.

Analytical results and ir spectra form the basis of the structure of the compounds. The ir spectra (KBr) show characteristic bands in the region 1350 cm⁻¹, 1510 cm⁻¹ and 760 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of sulphonamido group, thioureido linkage and substituted benzene ring.

Pharmacological screening (7-11) : Male Sprague-Dawley rats (100-125 g) were maintained on a low-iodide diet for 3 days, then divided into groups of four rats each. The animals in each group received an intraperitoneal injection of 1 ml of either a blank (0.9% NaCl), thiouracil or one of the test compounds. One hour after the administration of 1 μ Cu of Na¹³¹I, the animals were sacrificed and

the thyroids removed. The whole lobes were placed in ground glass homogenizing tubes and counted in a Nuclear-Chicago well scintillation counter to determine total iodide uptake. The whole lobes were then homogenized in 1 ml of 0.05 M barbital buffer (pH 8.6) containing 1.0 × 10⁻⁵ M thiouracil. 1 ml of cold 20% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added and the homogenate centrifuged. The precipitate was washed twice with 1.0 ml of cold 10% TCA. The original supernatant liquid and the two washings were combined and the radioactivity was determined. The ¹³¹I in this fraction indicated inorganic ¹³¹I or TCA soluble ¹³¹I. The washed precipitate was counted in the homogenising tube. The radioactivity in this fraction indicated the PB¹³¹I (protein-bound iodine) or the TCA precipitable ¹³¹I. The counts were all corrected for counting efficiency and are expressed as disintegrations per minute.

All compounds were dissolved in saline for injection. Thiouracil was dissolved with heating to 55°. Compounds nos. 10 and 20 were only partially soluble in saline, EtOH or NH₄OH and therefore they were injected as a suspension in saline. All compounds were assayed at concentrations equimolar and ten times equimolar to 0.5 mg of

thiouracil (3.9 μ moles) and the biological effect was almost the same at both the doses. Table 1 summarizes the results of screening observations.

All compounds have antithyroid effects upto some extent and appear to inhibit incorporation of I_2 in a manner similar to thiouracil. Compounds nos. 2-5, 7-10 and 17-19 appear to be slightly more potent than thiouracil.

Mode of action and effect of substituents on anti-thyroid activity: The thioureylene linkage in these compounds is capable of forming an -SH grouping by enolisation. The suggestion has been made that the interference with thyroxine synthesis was by a direct reaction between iodine and sulphhydryl grouping to form a disulphide^{1,2}. Since this reaction proceeded at a rate considerably faster than the iodination of tyrosyl group, the competition could be quite favourable for diversion of iodine away from organic binding.

These data suggest that a disulphide bond in thyroid tissue is cleaved by antithyroid compounds containing thioureylene linkage to form a new disulphide bond. This formulation is supported by chemical studies in which thiourea was found to cleave the disulphide bond of cystine to yield the mixed disulphide S-guanylthio-l-cysteine^{1,3}.

It is evident from the results of pharmacological studies that the introduction of chloro group in benzene ring enhances the activity to some extent.

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References

1. D. CAMPBELL, F. W. LANDGREBE and T. N. N. MORGAN, *Lancet*, 1944, **246**, 630.
2. E. J. BAUMANN, N. METZGER and D. MARINE, *Endocrinology*, 1944, **34**, 44.
3. C. H. LI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1065.
4. R. H. WILLIAMS, A. R. WEINGLASS and G. A. KAY, *Amer. J. Med. Sci.*, 1944, **207**, 701.
5. F. B. DAINS, R. Q. BRWSTER and C. P. OLANDER, *Org. Synth. Coll.*, **1**, 447.
6. J. W. McFARLAND and R. W. HOUSER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1968, **33**, 340.
7. C. S. PITTMAN and E. E. JONES, *Endocrinology*, 1963, **73**, 403.
8. R. PITTMAN, V. GALTON and N. S. HALMI, *Endocrinology*, 1958, **63**, 699.
9. W. D. ALEXANDER and J. WOLF, "Current Topics in Thyroid Research", Proceedings of the International Thyroid Conference, 5th, Rome, 1965, p. 271.
10. V. A. GALTON and R. PITT-RIVERS, *Endocrinology*, 1959, **64**, 835.
11. R. PITT-RIVERS, *Ann. N. Y. Acad. Sci.*, 1960, **86**, 362.
12. E. B. ASTWOOD, *Harvey Lectures, Ser.*, 1944-45, **40**, 195-235, Science Press, Lancaster, Pa.
13. G. TOENNIES, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1937, **120**, 297.

Chemical Investigation of *Wrightia mollissima*

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WRIGHTIA (fam. Apocyanaceae) is a genus of shrubs and small trees distributed in tropical Africa, Asia and Australia¹. The genus owe its importance both from its economic and medicinal points of view. The medicinal properties of *W. mollissima* are similar to *W. tinctoria* and *Holarrhena antidysenterica*, whose bark is used medicinally as a drug in amoebic dysentery. Survey of literature reveals that no work has been done previously on this plant. Hence a chemical investigation of its stem and leaves was undertaken. We have isolated α -amyrin acetate, taraxerol acetate, lupenone, taraxerol and β -sitosterol from petroleum ether extract while no crystalline compound could be isolated from ethanolic extract.

Finely powdered stem and leaves were extracted with petroleum ether (60°-80°) in Soxhlet apparatus followed by extraction with ethanol.

Petroleum ether extract: It was concentrated under reduced pressure to a semi solid mass, which was chromatographed over silica gel.

α -Amyrin acetate: Elution of column with hexane and benzene (3:1) yield α -amyrin acetate as white crystalline compound (chloroform-methanol), m.p. 225°-6°. Alkaline hydrolysis yielded α -amyrin, m.p. 194°-5°. Identical (m.m.p., tlc and ir) with authentic sample.

Taraxerol acetate: Elution of the column with hexane-benzene (1:1) furnished white needles (chloroform) of taraxerol acetate, m.p. 295°-7°. Alkaline hydrolysis gave taraxerol, m.p. 282°-3°. Identity confirmed by comparison (m.m.p., tlc and ir) with authentic sample.

Lupenone: Further elution of the column with benzene gave lupenone as white crystals (ether), m.p. 170°-1°, NaBH₄ reduction gave lupeol, m.p. 215°. Identical (m.m.p., tlc and ir) with authentic sample.

Taraxerol: Elution of the column with benzene also yielded taraxerol as fine needles (chloroform-methanol), m.p. 282°-3°, acetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 295°. Finally confirmed by comparison (m.m.p., tlc and ir) with authentic sample.

β -Sitosterol: Elution of the column with benzene-ethylacetate (98:2) furnished white crystals (chloroform-methanol) of β -sitosterol, m.p. 135°-7°, acetate (Ac₂O/pyr), m.p. 128°. Identical (m.m.p., tlc and ir) with authentic sample.

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